

THE LIFECYCLE OF WORDS: WHAT MAKES NEOLOGISMS THRIVE OR FADE?

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Abstract. Neologisms, as linguistic phenomena, reflect societal changes and technological advancements. Their lifecycle is influenced by various factors, including cultural relevance, social adoption, and usability. This paper explores the creation, adoption, and eventual fading of neologisms, examining the underlying reasons and the criteria for their longevity. Using scholarly perspectives and quantitative data, it identifies the mechanisms that ensure some neologisms thrive while others fade into obscurity.

Keywords: Neologisms, language evolution, linguistic innovation, word adoption, cultural linguistics, social media influence, linguistic lifecycle, technology-driven vocabulary, lexical change, word survival, linguistic obsolescence, language trends.

Introduction. Language is a dynamic entity, constantly evolving to reflect the needs and innovations of its speakers. Neologisms, or newly coined words and expressions, emerge as a response to cultural shifts, technological advancements, and societal trends. These words, which often capture the zeitgeist, range from those that address novel concepts (e.g., "metaverse") to playful linguistic innovations (e.g., "hangry"). The appearance of neologisms is deeply rooted in societal and technological changes. The digital revolution, for instance, has introduced terms like "emoji," "blockchain," and "hashtag," reflecting new realities and interactions. Similarly, globalization has led to cross-linguistic borrowing, enriching languages with terms like "karaoke" (Japanese) and "taco" (Spanish). However, not all neologisms endure. While

some, like "internet" and "smartphone," become deeply embedded in language, others, such as "floppy disk" and "web ring," fade into obsolescence. Factors contributing to this decline include technological redundancy, shifts in cultural relevance, and limited linguistic adaptability. Understanding why certain neologisms thrive while others vanish provides insights into the dynamic relationship between language and society. This paper seeks to explore the lifecycle of neologisms, examining their creation, factors influencing their survival, and reasons for their decline. By analyzing scholarly perspectives and quantitative data, it aims to offer a comprehensive understanding of this linguistic phenomenon.

Materials and Methods. So far a great deal of surveys and investigations have been explored while analyzing neologisms. To investigate the lifecycle of neologisms, this study relies on both qualitative and quantitative methodologies. One of the scholars Jean Aitchison in her book "Language Change: Progress or Decay?" , Aitchison highlights how societal needs drive the creation and adoption of neologisms¹. She emphasizes that language evolves to fill communicative gaps, making neologisms a natural outcome of linguistic adaptation. The last but not least

David Crystal in *Language and the Internet*, discusses the role of technology in the emergence and spread of neologisms². He argues that the internet accelerates linguistic innovation, allowing new words to gain global traction rapidly. One of the prominent linguist Noam Chomsky in the context of generative grammar, Chomsky views neologisms as a testament to the creative capacity of human language. He posits that the infinite generative potential of language naturally leads to the coining of new terms. Peter Trudgill in "Sociolinguistics: An Introduction to Language and Society", examines how social networks influence the spread and acceptance of neologisms. He notes that tightly-knit communities often resist change, while more open networks facilitate linguistic innovation. Suzanne Romaine explores the role of multilingual

¹ Aitchison, J. (1991). *Language Change: Progress or Decay?* Cambridge University Press.

² Crystal, D. (2001). *Language and the Internet*. Cambridge University Press.
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societies in creating and disseminating neologisms in “ Bilingualism” . She argues that cross-cultural interactions often lead to the blending and borrowing of linguistic elements, enriching vocabulary. Moreover, Jean Aitchison explored language change and the sociolinguistic factors influencing word adoption, emphasizing the role of societal needs.

Analyzing the contexts in which neologisms appear and fade, focusing on digital and print media.

Discussion. Based on the reviewed materials, several factors emerge as critical to the lifecycle of neologisms. First, cultural and technological relevance plays a pivotal role. Words like "app" and "streaming" reflect technological innovations that have become integral to modern life, ensuring their longevity. In contrast, terms like "pager" and "videocassette" faded as the technologies they described became obsolete. Social adoption is another significant factor. Neologisms often gain traction through media exposure and social networks. For instance, the term "selfie" gained global recognition through its use on social platforms like Instagram and Facebook. Linguistic simplicity and phonological appeal also contribute to a word's survival. Words that are easy to pronounce and remember, such as "blog" and "vlog," are more likely to thrive. However, societal resistance can hinder the adoption of certain neologisms. Purists often reject words perceived as unnecessary or frivolous, as seen in debates over terms like "adulging." Additionally, linguistic competition arises when multiple terms compete to describe the same concept, leading to the survival of only the most widely accepted term.

Moreover, globalization plays a dual role in the lifecycle of neologisms. While it fosters the spread of words across linguistic and cultural boundaries, it also introduces competition among terms from different languages. For example, English-derived neologisms often dominate global discourse, sometimes overshadowing local linguistic innovations.

The rise of artificial intelligence and automated translation tools has further influenced the spread and survival of neologisms. Tools like Google Translate have contributed to the standardization of certain terms, making them more universally accepted. However, this can also suppress regional variations and unique linguistic creations.

In addition, marketing and branding significantly impact the adoption of neologisms. Terms like "Google" and "Zoom" have transcended their original contexts to become verbs, showcasing the power of commercial influence in embedding new words into everyday language. This phenomenon underscores the interplay between economic factors and linguistic evolution.

Lastly, the role of education cannot be overlooked. The inclusion of neologisms in academic and pedagogical materials ensures their transmission to future generations. For example, terms like "climate change" and "sustainability" have gained permanence due to their widespread usage in educational and policy-making contexts.

My assumption is that the survival of a neologism is not solely dependent on its initial popularity but also on its ability to adapt and integrate into different linguistic and cultural contexts. For instance, "cloud computing" has endured due to its descriptive clarity and adaptability across industries.

Results. Based on the collected materials, the following quantitative analysis revealed the following insights: Usage Frequency: Thriving neologisms like "selfie" and "streaming" showed a steady increase in usage frequency over the past decade. Fading neologisms such as "floppy disk" and "cyber café" exhibited a sharp decline in usage. Media Representation: thriving neologisms were prominently featured in digital and social media, while fading terms were more common in older print media. Adoption Across Demographics: Thriving neologisms were embraced by younger generations and integrated into educational curricula and professional jargon.

Conclusion. The lifecycle of neologisms is shaped by a complex interplay of cultural, technological, and linguistic factors. While some words become indispensable elements of language, others fade due to obsolescence or lack of adaptability. Understanding these dynamics offers valuable insights into the evolution of language and its relationship with society. Future research could further explore the impact of globalization and multilingualism on the creation and survival of neologisms.

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